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Research Article

Using Physico– Chemical Analysis of Water Quality of Gauthami- Godavari Estuaries Chinnavalasala Village, Tallarevu Mandal, East Godavari District and Andhra Pradesh, India.

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Abstract: This study was aimed to estimate current status of Physico-chemical characteristics of Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries Chinnavalasala Village, Tallarevu Mandal, East Godavari District, and Andhra Pradesh. Monthly changes in physico-chemical parameters such as water temperature, P^H, Hardness, Dissolved Oxygen, Alkalinity, Salinity, and Carbon Dioxide were analyze for a period of one year from 1st July 2013 – 30th June 2013. The variation of the physico-chemical properties of water samples directly influences the biotic communities and primary productivity of the water bodies at Chinnavallasala Village.

Key Words: -Physico-Chemical parameters, Monthly variation of Temperature, P^H, Hardness, Dissolved Oxygen, Alkalinity, Salinity, and Carbon Dioxide.

INTRODUCTION

Chinnavalasala village is at nearly 25 km distance to the Kakinada city and 26 km distance to the Bay of Bengal and 15 km distance to the Koringa Mangroves. The Village covered with nearly 2,000 populations. The 90% peoples are Fisher men Remaining 10% Peoples are Farmers. Reliance K.G. Basin is situated to this village at 10 km distance. Water resources are of critical importance to both natural ecosystem and human development. The healthy aquatic ecosystem is depended on the Physico-chemical and biological characteristics. The quality of water in any ecosystem provides significant information about the available resources for supporting life in those ecosystem. To asses that monitoring of these parameters is essential to identify magnitude and source of any pollution load. These characteristics can identify certain condition for the ecology of living organisms and

suggest appropriate conservation and management strategies. In order to assess water quality index we have carried out the physico-chemical analysis of water Resources. The aim of the study is too reveled out the pollution status of River in terms of physico-chemical characteristics of water. However, very little information is available in relation to physico-chemical characteristics of water in the Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries, at Chinnavalasala, Tallarevu Mandal, East Godavari District and Andhra Pradesh. Hence, the present study was conducted to study the physico-chemical properties of water in the Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries, at Chinnavalasala, Tallarevu Mandal, East Godavari District for a period of one year from *1st July 2013 to 30th June 2014*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of water samples: In order to determine the water quality index, three stations were chosen for sample collection from the Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries *1st July 2013 to 30th June 2014* in the first week of every month. The water samples were collected in polythene bottles of capacity 1 to 2 liter in the month at 15 days intervals between 9.00 a.m. to 11.00 a.m. These samples were collected from approximately 15-20 cm below the water surface. Care must be taken not to catch any floating material or bed material into the container. The standard procedures were adopted for the determination of physico-chemical parameters. Methods employed for determination of physico-chemical parameters **Table-1**

Table 1:Methods employed for determination of physico-chemical parameters

Sr. No.	Parameters	Methods employed
01	pH	pH metry
02	Temperature	Thermometry
03	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	Wrinklersmethod
04	Alkalinity	Titration
05	Hardness	EDTA titration
06	Salinity	Titration
07	Carbon Dioxide	Titration

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The monthly values of physico-chemical parameters Temperature, pH, Hardness, Dissolved oxygen, Alkalinity, Salinity and Carbon Dioxide of Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries water at the location of the present study area were shown in **Table-2**.

Table 2: Water parameters prescribed by ISI, ICMR and BIS

	Temperature	P ^H	Salinity	Alkalinity	Hardness	Dissolved Oxygen	Carbon Dioxide
January	32	7.4	1.2	84	265	4.8	1.89
February	31	8.0	1.3	93	350	5.6	0.99
March	31	7.7	0.2	86	132	6.9	0.89
April	30	8.4	0.9	145	132	4.5	1.89
May	34	7.9	0	124	145	6.2	1.99
Jun	30	7.5	0.6	130	142	7.5	5.99
July	26	8.1	1.1	144	132	1.6	0.99
Augusta	30	7.8	0.5	132	125	4.8	1.89
September	32	7.6	0.6	87	136	5.2	3.90
October	31	7.7	0.4	199	127	4.8	1.89
November	30	7.6	0.3	133	250	7.8	0.99
December	29	7.7	2.2	118	295	2.1	3.90

Temperature: There is a closed relation between the atmospheric temperature and water temperature. Air temperature is one of the most important ecological factors which control the physiological behavior of the aquatic system and distribution of the microorganisms. The temperature of the collected water samples varies in between 26⁰C to 34⁰C.

Figure 1: Seasonal variations in the water temperature in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin.

pH of the collected water sample: It was observed that pH of the water normally remains higher in summer and in rainy seasons. It depends on photosynthetic activity. It was relatively more in winter. It was almost same during summer and monsoon. The variation occurs in the pH values due to change

in the values of CO₂, carbonate and bicarbonate in the water. In the present study the pH values in all the collected water samples ranges from 7.4 to 8.4 which are all within the limit.

Figure 2: Seasonal variations in the water pH in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin

Salinity: The total Salinity in all the collected water samples of Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries was found in the range of 0 mg/L to 2.2 mg/L.

Figure 3: Seasonal variations in the water salinity in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin.

Alkalinity: Alkalinity of water is measure of its capacity to neutralize acids. Bicarbonates are formed in considerable amount from the action of carbon dioxide upon basic materials in soil and other salts of weak acids. Alkalinity in the dam water caused by bicarbonate as carbonates values in all the collected samples ranges from 84 mg/L to 145 mg/L.

Figure 4: Seasonal variations in the water alkalinity in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin

Hardness: The total hardness in all the collected water samples of Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries was found in the range of 125 mg/L to 295 mg/L.

Figure 5: Seasonal variations in the water hardness in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO): DO is one of the most important parameter in assessing water quality and understanding the physical and biological process prevailing in the water. The importance of DO was reported by many researchers because DO in aquatic ecosystem brings out various biochemical changes and it influence on metabolic activities on organisms. Good quality water should have the solubility of oxygen 1.6 mg/L. DO was maximum in winter while minimum in summer season. The DO of the collected water samples is about 7.8 mg/L. It is quite close to the prescribed values.

Figure 6: Seasonal variations in the water dissolved oxygen in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin

Carbon Dioxide: High Carbon Dioxide ion concentration indicates organic pollution in the water. The amount of Carbon Dioxide in all the collected water samples of Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries was found in the range of 0.99 mg/L to 5.99 mg/L.

Figure 7: Seasonal variations in the water carbon dioxide in Gauthami- Godavari Estuariesin.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the water quality parameters of Gauthami-Godavari Estuaries shows that Temperature, pH, Hardness, Dissolved oxygen, Alkalinity, Salinity and Carbon Dioxide values are well within the permissible limits. Habited water is generally used by animals, birds and aquatic life. After physico-chemical analysis we found that the sample of potable water and habited water are free pollution and ecologically balanced.

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